

A LITTLE STUDIED AND DIFFERENT GROUP OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVE PRESERVATIVES, MEDICINAL PLANTS AND PRODUCTS

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Abstract: Nowadays, traditional medicine (folk medicine) is the wisdom of the people. It is a very rich and vast body of knowledge infused with experience. It is an inexhaustible resource that enriches scientific (official) medicine with new, effective medicinal preparations. The value and role of folk medicine in this area is priceless. As an example, it is enough to remember that most of the medicinal plants used in modern medicine were taken from the treasury of folk medicine, and modern scientific medicine itself developed on the basis of folk medicine.

Key words: folk medicine, pharmacognosy, medicinal plants, Chaga, raspberry, levzeia, orthosiphon, peony, eucommia, kalanchoi, coral, pumpkin seeds, mountain yarrow, onion, garlic.

It is known that the science of pharmacognosy consists of 2 parts, in the 1st part, general issues related to the science, the historical development of the science, and in the 2nd part, i.e., in the special part, one of the main issues is the biological composition of medicinal plants. They are divided into groups according to the chemical structure of active substances, for example, phenol glycosides, anthracin products, flavonoids, etc., or according to their physiological effects, for example, vitamins, cardiac glycosides, bitter substances, etc. .

But there are also such medicinal plants that contain various substances both chemically and physiologically. Some medicinal plants are used effectively in medicine, but the biologically active substances contained in them have not yet been sufficiently studied. Such medicinal plants and products are grouped together.

They include the following plants:

We can give examples of chaga, raspberry, levzeyia, orthosiphon, peony, eucommia, kalanchoe, coral tree, pumpkin seeds, mountain kuddu, onion, garlic and others.

Let's go through the first 5 medicinal plants mentioned above.

Black fungus or chaga on a birch tree - *Fungus betulinus* The name of the plant. *Oblique inonotus (chaga) - Inonotus obliquus*. Family. *Hymenochaetaceae* belongs to the *Hymenochaetaceae* family. A fungus that grows parasitically on the bark of a birch tree. The spore of this fungus falls through the air to the crack in the bark of a birch tree and forms a fungal mycelium. Micellar threads (bodies) go to the wood of the tree and begin to rot, but the body of inonotus, which consists of these fungal threads, continues to grow and reaches 3-5 kg in 10-15 years. This is the asexual body of the fungus growing from the trunk of the tree. The asexual body that produces basidiospores is under the bark and is not visible. Places of growth. *Inonotus* grows only on the bark of the birch tree. It is abundant in birch groves of Belarus, the Baltic states, and the northern regions of Russia. Product preparation. Mushrooms can be collected all year round. It is collected from cut young and

old birch trees. There are no fungi in young birch trees. The fungus on the tree is a round or oblong, 30-40 cm in diameter, 10-15 cm thick (sometimes up to 1.5 m long) bulging black tumor. The fungus consists of three layers: a black, cracked and bulging outer layer, a brown, very hard middle layer, and a porous and soft inner layer. The inner layer of the mushroom is not harvested. The mushroom is chopped with an ax and removed from the bark and woody part of the tree. It is dried at a temperature of -60°C . Appearance of the product. The finished product consists of dried, crushed pieces of up to 10 cm in size, dark brown, with a cracked black top, hard, variously shaped pieces of fungus. The product should be stored in a dry place as it absorbs moisture quickly. The product is odorless, has a bitter taste. Chemical composition. The active substances of the fungus are complex and may consist of pigments close to chromones and anthocyanins - a chromogenic complex. When these complexes are hydrolyzed, they are broken down into phenolaldehydes, polyphenols, aromatic oxyacids and their quinones. The fungus contains up to 20% of such a complex, which dissolves in water and forms a colloidal solution. In addition, it contains agaric acid, organic acids, triterpenoid inotodiol, a small amount of alkaloids, various trace elements.

Agaricin acid

Usage. Medicinal preparations of the product are used in the treatment of inoperable cancer and gastrointestinal diseases (chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, etc.). These drugs have the effect of stopping the growth of tumors and slightly improving the patient's condition. Medicinal preparations. Dark extract, tincture, befungin, BIN tablet, BINAN 8 tablet.

Raspberry fruit - *Fructus rubi idaei* The name of the plant. Ordinary raspberry - *Rubus idaeus* Family. Rosaceae - rhododendrons. Raspberries are semi-shrubs up to 1-2 m tall. Two-year-old above-ground branches grow from the rhizome. The first-year branches are green, non-woody, with small thorns and do not bear fruit. It remains and blooms next year in June-July. After the fruit ripens, the old stem dries up. New stems grow from the rhizome every year. They are located in a row. Those on the upper part of the stem are often 3-lobed. The leaves are ovate, hairless on the top, hairy on the bottom. plangan. The calyx is cut into 5, it remains with the fruit. There are 5 crowns, many fathers and mothers. The fruit is a red, grained, complex hard fruit. It blooms in June-July, the fruit ripens in July-August. Geographic distribution. Almost all of them grow and are cultivated in the forests of Central Asia. Product preparation. Ripe fruits are harvested by hand in good weather. It is dried thinly, then spread to a thickness of 2.5-3.5 cm and dried in dryers at $50-60^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is separated from the black ones. Appearance of the product. The finished product consists of a dried fruit. The fruit is complex and consists of 30-60 individual grains. Each grain is small, egg-shaped, one-seeded, the upper side is pitted and covered with hairs. The product has a gray-red tint, a slightly aromatic smell and a sour-sweet taste. The fruit should be stored in a dry place. Chemical composition. The fruit contains organic acids (up to 22% malic, lemon, salicylate, wine, formic and other acids), up to 45 mg % vitamin C, sugars, anocyanins, flavoring substances, etc. The seed contains 14.6% fat, 0

Contains 7% sitosterol. Usage. The product is used as an antiperspirant for colds. The juice is used to improve the taste of liquid medicines. Medicinal preparations. Tincture, juice. The fruit is included in antiperspirant teas - collections.

Leuzea root with rhizome - Rhizomata cum radicibus leuzeae. Asteraceae - Asteraceae. It is a perennial herb, 50-180 cm tall. The rhizome is woody, thick, branched, and is located horizontally underground. There are several stems, unbranched, finely striped. The leaf is simple, the general appearance is elliptic or oblong-ovate, divided into 5-8 deep feathery lobes. The flowers are collected in a large spherical basket. The leaves of the basket are multi-rowed, yellow, lancet-shaped. located below. Its fruit is pistachio. It blooms in July-August.

Geographical distribution. It grows in mountainous areas (at an altitude of 1700-2000 m), in meadows, in open areas of mountain forests, in valleys. In the mountainous areas of Siberia, Eastern Kazakhstan (Sayan, Altai, Jungar Olatog) found in. Product preparation. The product is dug up in August-September, cleaned and dried in the sun. Plantation partners are collected when they are 3-4 years old. Appearance of the product. The finished product consists of a slightly bent, hollow rhizome covered with small roots. The length of the rhizome is 12 cm, the thickness is 0.6-2.6 cm, the root is 3-15 cm, the thickness is 0.5 cm. The root is strong, it does not break when bent, and the stems built on the rhizome remain established. The upper side of the root and rhizome is dark brown to black, and the inside is pale yellow. It has a unique smell, sweeter, tarry taste. Chemical composition. The product contains 0.1% ascorbic acid, carotene, inulin, triterpene saponins - phytoecdysoids, lignans, sabin alkaloids, essential oil, aromatic acids, 5% additives, etc. The main active substances of Lavzey are lignans and phytoecdysoids. Use. Its drugs are used as a medicine to raise the tone of the body in functional disorders of the nervous system, physical fatigue of the brain and body, and other serious diseases.

Medicinal preparations. Liquid extract. The tonic drink "Sayan" is made from the product. Ecdysten is a medicine that increases the tone of the body.

Rhododendron and root and above-ground part of peonies - Rhizomata et radices, herba peoniae The name of the plant. Peony - *Paeonia anomala*.

Family. Aiktovanodoshka - Ranunculaceae. Ranunculaceae is a perennial herb growing 60-100 cm tall. The rhizome is multi-headed, horizontal and large. The stem is several, erect, unbranched, the base is covered with thick scales. Leaves are 3-5, simple, glabrous, deeply cut into 3 lobes twice, or divided feathery. The ones in the middle are three-lobed, the ones next to them are lancet-shaped, with straight edges. They are located in a row on the stem with a band of leaves. The flowers are large and singly located on the third part of the stem. sometimes light red color, 8 (sometimes more). The fruit is multi-seeded, consisting of 3-5 leaves. It blooms in May-June, the fruit ripens in August. Geographical distribution. MXDs It is found in the forests of Eastern Kazakhstan in the European part. Product preparation. The upper part of the soil is harvested when the plant blooms (May-June). It is dried at 45-60°C. The underground organs are dug up in autumn or spring, separated from the stem, dried at 45-60°. Appearance of the product. The finished product consists of some topsoil and rhizomes and roots. The rhizomes and roots are of various shapes, 1-2 cm long, 0.2-1.5 cm thick, twisted lengthwise, and the upper side is dark brown or yellowish-brown in color. , consisting of yellowish-yellow particles. It breaks unevenly when rubbed. Rhizomes and roots have a sweeter, slightly astringent taste

and a strong, specific smell. Chemical composition. The product contains up to 1.6% essential oil, salicin glycoside, 73.5% starch, 1.66-2.6% iridoids, saponins, alkaloids, additives, trace elements. It is used as a sedative in neurosthenia, insomnia. Medicinal preparations. Nastoyka (prepared from 40% alcohol). A 10% tincture of peony root extract has a calming effect on the nervous system without changing the respiratory function and blood pressure.

Orthosiphon leaf - Folia orthosiphonis The name of the plant. Orthosiphon (kidney tea) - Orthosiphon stamineus Family. Samiaceae - Perennial, evergreen semi-shrub or shrub, 1-1.5 m tall. The stem is several, 4-sided, the base is woody, the lower part is dark purple, the upper part is green-purple or green, and the joints are painted purple. It is established. The flowers are clustered like a ball and form a shingle-like flower. The flower is curved, white and purple in color. The calyx is bell-shaped, double-lipped, the corolla is also double-lipped, 4 male nodes, 4 female nodes. Varnished, located above. The fruit consists of 1-4 nuts. It blooms in July-August. Geographic distribution. Cultivated in Indonesia, Java Islands, Georgia. Product preparation. The tip of the plant branch together with 2 pairs of leaves (flash) is picked by hand 5-6 times a year, spread in the shade for 24-36 hours, then dried at 30-35°C. 'appearance. The finished product consists of a dried 2-cm-long branch with 2 pairs of leaves (flash).

The leaf is oblong ovate or rhomboid, sharp-pointed, serrated, hairy on the underside, 2-5 cm long, 1.5-2 cm wide. The product is odorless, has a slightly bitter, astringent taste. Chemical composition. The product contains triterpene saponins, inositol, bitter orthosiphon glycoside, up to 1.5% wine, citric and other acids, 0.2-0.66% essential oil, 5-6% additives, a large amount of potassium salts. . Usage. Ortosiphon drug is used as a diuretic in diseases of the II-III degree of the cardiovascular system in combination with kidney (kidney stone disease) and cholecystitis and cardiac glycosides. Medicinal preparations. Drip.

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